
Business Information Sciences with Special Reference to the Digital Marketing and SEO as a field of study

P. K. Paul¹, P. S. Aithal²

¹Raiganj University (RGU), West Bengal, India

²Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

¹Corresponding Author: P.K. Paul & email: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

Abstract

Information Science is changing and increasing day by day. The applications and integration of Technologies and Computing components leads the nature of Information Science. In early days Information Science was mainly concentrated in the manual documentation and information management techniques and tools and gradually the concept has been changed and shifted towards automation systems. The application of IT and Computing including Information Management is simply Information Science. The increasing role of Information Science in different field leads the development of various other domains viz. Health Information Science, Geo Information Science, Business Information Science etc. The domain of Business Information Sciences is a large field and in terms of techniques and tools it is deals with Business Intelligence, Enterprise Resource Planning, Business and Data warehousing, Search Engine Optimization, Business Analytics etc. In smaller context it is called as Business Informatics. Hence it is also related with the areas of E Business, E Commerce, Digital/E Marketing etc. Among the areas of Business Information Science Search Engine Optimization and Digital Marketing are emerging rapidly and this study shows the emerging context of offering the area as a program of study. Moreover the paper provides an overview of other areas uses in Business Information Science including its nature.

Keywords: *Business Informatics, Business IT, Information Science and Technology, Digital Marketing, SEO, Educational Programs, India, Development, Private Universities*

Introduction

Business Information Science is a combination of the area of Business and informatics. Business Information Science is a skill focused domain for the design, development, management and

promotion of the IT Systems for the business and institutions. Business Information Science is commonly called as Business Informatics program as ‘Informatics’ and ‘Information Science’ both are considered as synonym [1], [6]. Within Business Informatics area there are many matches with the area of IT Management, Information Systems Management, IT Policy Management, Management Information Systems (MIS) etc. Business Informatics is responsible for the creation of digital business and transformation of business into new age venture. As far as latest Business Informatics tools are concerned, one of the important is—Search Engine Optimization; and broadly it is considered as an important area of Digital Marketing. Many academicians international treats Digital Marketing as an important area and part of Business Informatics. SEO is an art for making websites visible in the search engine by using appropriate tools and methods. Importantly, Digital Marketing and SEO are offered as an educational programs in international universities. Moreover very few Indian universities and educational institutions have started programs in this field at Bachelors and Masters level with various focus/ disciplines [2], [7], [14].

Objective

The Paper is conceptual, interdisciplinary in nature and deals with various aim, objectives and agenda viz.

- To learn about the basics of Business Information Science including its nature, characteristics; briefly.
- To know about the basics areas and parts of the Business Information Science in brief manner.
- To learn about the latest and emerging nomenclatures and subject within Business Information Science.
- To learn about the basics of Digital Marketing including its nature, characteristics and functions.
- To learn about the basics of Higher Education Systems in India with reference to possible Digital Marketing area.
- To dig out the basic overview of SEO including the role of Digital Marketing as an educational and training program to generate new age skilled workforce to prepare Digital India empowered by Digital Marketing & Business.

Methodology

The current paper is conceptual in nature and deals with several areas (*viz. Business and Management, Computing and IT, Planning and Policy Studies*) and thus several methods have been undertaken. Initially reviews of literature were undertaken and gradually other methods viz. web and internet review was undertaken. As concepts of Business Informatics, Digital Marketing

and SEO are emerging and traditional documents are less and thus online means have been used. Major search engine/ portals of scientific documents have been used (Google Scholar/ Scopus/ Science Direct etc). Indian higher education system has been mapped with the sources from the MHRD, UGC's appropriate sites etc. General search engine has been used by using appropriate search keywords viz. MBA Digital Marketing in India. Hence the study mainly restricted to MBA space of Digital Marketing and ignores other areas.

Business Information Science: Basics

As we learn about the integration of Business Studies/ Management and Informatics/Information Science has created the domain Business Information Science for the solution in respect of Business Information and technological solution [3], [7], [10]. Business Informatics/ Information Science nomenclature is closely associated with the following area and concepts viz.—

- Business fundamentals and Organization of Information
- IT Infrastructure building
- Management Information Systems (including designing and development)
- Enterprise Resource Planning and ES
- Decision Support Systems etc.

Business Information Science is the key player in modern Information Age and a rising branch in Information Science and Technology. As far as tools, techniques and technologies it is deals with various areas. Though in terms of Technology core it is mainly deals with the following —

- Business Intelligence (BI)
- Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP).
- Data Base Management Systems (DBMS)
- Business and Data Warehousing (including Data Mining)
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and Allied Areas
- Business Analytics and Optimization etc

Business Information Science is smaller than Business Information Technology and in European countries it is called as Business Informatics. Conceptually it is also deals with the following core areas—

- Digital Business/ E-Business
- E-Commerce
- Digital Marketing / eMarketing

Business Informatics in terms of interdisciplinary context is normally associated with the areas mentioned below (but not limited to)—

- IT Governance and Administration
- IT Policy & Planning
- IT Management
- Information Management and Administration

As a whole Business Information Science is deals with various attributes and areas viz. Technologies, Core Business areas and sectors from the Management.

Fig: 1 The Stakeholders/ areas in Business Informatics

Digital Marketing: Basics

When marketing of products and or services done by the digital technologies such as by the internet, mobile phones, display advertising and different type of other digital medium that is called Digital Marketing [4], [5], [8].

The concept of Digital Marketing evolved in 1990s though in 2000s the traditional concept has been changed as a large number of firms and organizations use technology for business and specially marketing. Marketing plans and etc in digital space has been changed rapidly in recent past. Moreover the common people using digital devices for marketing and similar affairs and thus physical shops, digital marketing etc become important and valuable [5], [9], [13].

There are numerous methods and technologies have risen in recent past in the area of Digital Marketing viz.

- Search engine optimization (SEO)
- Search engine marketing (SEM)
- Content marketing and Automation
- Campaign marketing,
- Data-driven marketing
- Social Media Optimization etc

Apart from these there are lot in the Digital Marketing areas viz. influencer marketing, e-commerce marketing, social media marketing, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising etc are rising in recent past [4], [8], [11]. In recent past the area of digital marketing also extends and includes other digital media systems such as mobile phone based services viz. SMS and MMS, callback, and on-hold mobile ring tones etc.

Digital Marketing and Digital Business: Need

The traditional marketing and business strategies has been changed in recent past due to globalization of data and this digital transformation has been impacted on various space ranging from businesses; healthcare, corporate, governance etc [6], [12]. The growing IT Applications in business is accelerating business activities and allied affairs for leverage opportunities in a strategically. Ultimately introducing IT in business leads the concepts of the following—

- Enhancing Data and information availability in different space and segments for the business affairs.
- To do better and healthy decision making of the business houses and corporate bodies as much as possible.

- For better and strategic activities of the management with the help of management tools, techniques and devices.
- To do the healthy IT applications in the HR, Financial and Marketing activities.
- To engage in better and healthy, effective information uses, business performance etc for the actual growth.

This kind of technologies and computing even applied in most traditional of industries, making a digital business in recent past. Moreover strategies have been employed in better storing and analyzing data for the competitive advantage of the Organizational Informatics Practice.

Search Engine Optimization and Digital Marketing: The Educational Models

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is an emerging area of Web Technology and also the emerging area of Marketing (more specifically Digital Marketing and Business). Though more technically it is the process of increasing online visibility of a website (or web page/ web portal) in a search engine unpaid results [10]. Normally such kind of efforts and methods are called as natural, organic, or earned results.

SEO may target different type of search which includes the search in image search, video search, audio search and other different form. And numerous areas viz. academic search, business search, news search etc. SEO is helps in gaining good results in the websites in the search engine and more specifically rank of a particular website.

Hence SEO is treated as one of the important, valuable and most gaining tool for the enhancement of the marketing and advertisement in digital way. Hence it is one of the important areas in Digital Marketing and broadly Business Informatics. Internationally many universities have started program on Digital Marketing (MSc), depicted in Table: 1 [10].

Table: 1-Few MSc program in Digital Marketing in International Universities

Digital Marketing Masters Programs in International Universities		
	Universities	Programs
1	SKEMA Business School	MSc Digital Marketing
2	University of Brighton , Switzerland	MSc Digital Marketing
3	University of Salford Manchester, Salford, UK	MSc Digital Marketing
4	Manchester Metropolitan University, UK	MSc Digital Marketing
5	The University of Hong Kong, China	MSc Digital Marketing

		Communications
6	Nottingham Trent University, UK	MSc Digital Marketing
7	University of South Wales, UK	MSc Strategic Digital Marketing

While in India many universities have started Digital marketing incorporated with the SEO and allied areas. As per the specified study and methodology following are few MBA program in the field of Digital Marketing only listed in Table: 2 [10].

Table: 2-Few MSc program in Digital Marketing in Indian Universities

Digital Marketing Masters Programs		
	Universities	Programs
1	Assam Down Town University	MBA (Digital Marketing) with TimesPrO
2	Kalinga University	MBA (Digital Marketing)
3	Shree Guru Gobind Singh Tricentenary University	MBA (Digital Marketing)
4	Rayat Bahra University	MBA (Digital Marketing)
5	RIMT University	MBA (Digital Marketing)
6	NIIT University	MBA (Digital Marketing)
7	ICFAI University, Tripura	MBA (Digital Marketing)
8	Teerthanker Mahaveer University, UP	MBA (Digital Marketing)
9	Adamas University, Kolkata	MBA (Digital Marketing)
10	University of Engineering and Management	MBA (Digital Marketing)
No. of Total Universities 10		Total PG Programs 10

Though many universities have been started Digital Marketing and another important area of Business Informatics i.e. E-Commerce as an integrated nomenclature Digital Marketing & E-Commerce with MBA Degree. The output of the study has been listed in Table: 3.

Table: 3-Few MSc program in Digital Marketing and allied areas in Indian Universities

Digital Marketing & Allied Masters Programs		
	Universities	Programs

1	Ajeenkya D.Y. Patil University	MBA (Digital Marketing & E-Commerce)
2	Centurion University of Technology and Management	MBA (Digital Marketing & E-Commerce)
3	Uttaranchal University, Dehradun	MBA (Digital Marketing & E-Commerce)
No. of Total Universities 3		Total PG Programs 3

Findings

- Business Informatics is one of the emerging area within domain specific Informatics/ Information Science.
- The core of the Business Informatics is from Management and Business, Information Studies and Management and Information Technology.
- Business Information Sciences may be considered as broadest branch while it is also called as Business Informatics, Organizational Informatics, Business IT, Business Information Systems etc.
- In technological space Search engine optimization (SEO) is an Important tool within Digital Marketing and additionally it also deals with other components viz. Search engine marketing (SEM), Content marketing and Automation, Campaign marketing, Data-driven marketing, Social Media Optimization etc
- In recent past Digital Marketing (incorporated with SEO) is started in the academic institutions leading to Bachelors and Masters Degrees.
- India is gaining well in respect of similar degrees and subjects in the field of Digital Marketing and Business, but still available in MBA degree rather BSc, MSc etc.

Concluding Remarks

The concept of digital business is rising by the adaptation of technology as an advantage in its internal and external operations of an institution. Information technology and computing has changed the IT and Information infrastructure and operation of businesses in different perspective since the computerization and later when Internet became widely available to businesses and individuals. This kind of advancement changed the way businesses conduct their day-to-day operations and as a result Business Informatics evolved. Initially only core IT components were the part of this digital movement but gradually different areas have emerged viz. cloud computing including IaaS, SaaS delivery

models, Big Data etc. The latest among these areas is SEO and it has become an important part for bringing new IT culture in business entities, affairs and agenda.

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